

INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER

p-ISSN 2992-9229

e-ISSN 3060-5318

TURKOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR

Xalqaro ilmiy jurnal

2025 №3
(8)

Samarqand-2025

p-ISSN 2992-9229

e-ISSN 3060-5318

TURKOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR

XALQARO ILMIY JURNALI

“TURKOLOGICAL RESEARCH” INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
JOURNAL

ULUSLARARASI “TÜRKOLOJİ ARAŞTIRMALARI” DERGİSİ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ “ТЮРКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ”

Jurnal rasmiy sayti: <https://turkologiya.samdu.uz/>

SAMARQAND – 2025

“TURKOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR”

XALQARO ILMIY JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL “TURKOLOGICAL RESEARCH”

ULUSLARARASI “TÜRKOLOJİ ARAŞTIRMALARI” BİLİMSEL DERGİSİ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ “ТЮРКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ”

Bosh muharrir:	Bosh muharrir o‘rinbosari:
Juliboy ELTAZAROV <i>f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston)</i>	Roxila RUZMANOVA <i>f.f.n., dotsent (O‘zbekiston)</i>
TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI:	
<p>Rustam XALMURADOV – t.f.d., professor, Sh.Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand davlat universiteti rektori (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Hakim XUSHVAQTOV – f.m.f.d., professor, Sh.Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand davlat universiteti ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo‘yicha prorektori (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Akmal AHATOV – t.f.d., professor, Sh.Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand davlat universiteti xalqaro hamkorlik bo‘yicha prorektori (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Muslihiddin MUHIDDINOV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Ibodulla MIRZAYEV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Shuhrat SIROJIDDINOV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Suyun KARIMOV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Murodqosim ABDIYEV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Azamat PARDAYEV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Musa YULDASHEV – f.f.n., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Dilfuza DJURAKULOVA – t.f.n., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Aftondil ERKINOV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Qosimjon SODIQOV – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p>	<p>Muhabbat QURBONOVA – f.f.d., professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Ali AKAR – f.f.d., professor (Turkiya);</p> <p>Abduselam ARVAS – f.f.d., professor (Turkiya);</p> <p>Funda TOPRAK – f.f.d., professor (Turkiya);</p> <p>Musa Shamil YUKSEL – f.f.d., professor (Turkiya);</p> <p>Temur KOJAO‘G‘LI – f.f.d., professor (AQSH);</p> <p>Hayrunnisa ALAN – f.f.d., professor (Turkiya);</p> <p>Varis CHAKAN – f.f.d., professor (Turkiya);</p> <p>Almaz ULVI – f.f.d., professor (Ozarbayjon);</p> <p>Emrah YILMAZ – Phd, dotsent (Turkiya);</p> <p>Foziljon SHUKUROV – Phd, dotsent (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Dilshod XURSANOVA – Phd, dotsent (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Shahnoza XUSHMURODOVA – DSc, professor (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Dinara ISLAMOVA – Phd, dotsent (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Feruza JUMANIYAZOVA – Phd, dotsent (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Istoda RASULOVA – Phd, dotsent (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Dilorom MUMINOVA – Phd, dotsent (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Zarifa XUSANOVA – Phd, dotsent (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Feruza MANUKYAN – Phd (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Mas’ul muharrir: PhD, dotsent Zokir BAYNAZAROV (O‘zbekiston);</p> <p>Texnik xodim: Raxmatulla SHOKIROV (O‘zbekiston).</p>

“TURKOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR” XALQARO ILMİY JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF “TURKOLOGICAL RESEARCH”

ULUSLARARASI “TÜRKOLÖJİ ARAŞTIRMALARI” BİLİMSEL DERGİSİ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ “ТЮРКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ”

Главный редактор:

Жулибой ЭЛТАЗАРОВ

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Рохила РУЗМАНОВА

к.ф.н., доцент (Узбекистан)

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Рустам ХАЛМУРАДОВ – д.т.н., профессор, ректор Самаркандского государственного университета имени Ш.Рашидова (Узбекистан);

Хаким ХУШВАКТОВ – д.ф.-м.н., профессор, проректор по научной работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного университета имени Ш.Рашидова (Узбекистан);

Акмал АХАТОВ – д.т.н., профессор, проректор по международному сотрудничеству Самаркандского государственного университета имени Ш.Рашидова (Узбекистан);

Муслихиддин МУХИДДИНОВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Ибодулла МИРЗАЕВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Шухрат СИРОЖИДДИНОВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Суюн КАРИМОВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Муродкасым АБДИЕВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Азамат ПАРДАЕВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Муса ЮЛДАШЕВ – к.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Дилфуза ДЖУРАКУЛОВА – к.и.н., доцент (Узбекистан);

Афтондил ЭРКИНОВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Касимжон СОДИКОВ – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Мухаббат КУРБАНОВА – д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан);

Али АКАР – д.ф.н., профессор (Турция);

Абдуселам АРВАС – д.ф.н., профессор (Турция);

Фунда ТОПРАК – д.ф.н., профессор (Турция);

Муса Шамиль ЮКСЕЛЬ – д.ф.н., профессор (Турция);

Темур КОДЖАОГЛУ – д.ф.н., профессор (США);

Хайрунниса АЛАН – д.ф.н., профессор (Турция);

Барис ЧАКАН – д.ф.н., профессор (Турция);

Алмаз УЛЬВИ – д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан).

Эмрах ЙИЛМАЗ – PhD, доцент (Турция);

Фозилжон ШУКУРОВ – PhD, доцент (Узбекистан);

Дилшод ХУРСАНОВ – PhD, доцент (Узбекистан);

Шахноза ХУШМУРОДОВА – DSc, профессор (Узбекистан);

Динара ИСЛАМОВА – PhD, доцент (Узбекистан);

Феруза ДЖУМАНИЯЗОВА – PhD, доцент (Узбекистан);

Истода РАСУЛОВА – PhD, доцент (Узбекистан);

Дилором МУМИНОВА – PhD, доцент (Узбекистан);

Зарифа ХУСАНОВА – PhD, доцент (Узбекистан);

Феруза МАНУКЯН – Phd (Узбекистан);

Ответственный редактор: PhD, доцент **Зокир БАЙНАЗАРОВ** (Узбекистан)

Технический персонал: **Рахматулла ШОКИРОВ** (Узбекистан)

“TURKOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR” XALQARO ILMİY JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF “TURKOLOGICAL RESEARCH”
ULUSLARARASI “TÜRKOLOJİ ARAŞTIRMALARI” BİLİMSEL DERGİSİ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ “ТЮРКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ”

Chief Editor:/ Deputy Chief Editor:

Prof. Dr. Juliboy ELTAZAROV (Uzbekistan)
Ass. Prof. Dr. Rokhila RUZMANOVA (Uzbekistan)

Baş Editör:/ Baş Editör Yardımcısı:

Prof. Dr. Juliboy ELTAZAROV (Özbekistan)
Doç. Dr. Rohila RUZMANOVA (Özbekistan)

EDITORIAL TEAM:/ BİLİM KURULU:

Prof. Dr. Rustam KHALMURADOV – Rector of Samarkand State University named after Sh.Rashidov (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Hakim KHUSHVAKTOV – Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation, Samarkand State University named after Sh.Rashidov (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Akmal AKHATOV – Vice-Rector for International Cooperation of Samarkand State University named after Sh.Rashidov (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Muslihiddin MUKHIDDINOV (Uzbekistan)

Prof. Dr. Ibodulla MIRZAEV (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Shukhrat SIROJIDDINOV (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Suyun KARIMOV (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Murodkasim ABDIEV (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Azamat PARDAEV (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Musa YULDASHEV (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. Dr. Dilfuza DJURAKULOVA (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Aftondil ERKINOV (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Kasimjon SODIKOV (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Muhabbat KURBANOVA (Uzbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Ali AKAR (Turkey);

Prof. Dr. Abdusalam ARVAS (Turkey);

Prof. Dr. Funda TOPRAK (Turkey);

Prof. Dr. Musa Shamil YUKSEL (Turkey);

Prof. Dr. Temur KOJAĞLU (USA);

Prof. Dr. Hayrunnisa ALAN (Turkey);

Prof. Dr. Varis ÇAKAN (Turkey);

Prof. Dr. Almaz ULVI (Azerbaijan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Emrah YILMAZ (Turkey);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Foziljon SHUKUROV (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Dilshod KHURSANOV (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Shakhnoza KHUSHMURODOVA (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Dinara İSLAMOVA (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Feruza JUMANIYAZOVA (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Istoda RASULOVA (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Dilorom MUMİNOVA (Uzbekistan);

Ass. Prof. PhD. Zarifa HUSANOVA (Uzbekistan);

PhD. Feruza MANUKYAN (Uzbekistan);

Managing editor: *Ass. Prof. PhD. Zokir BAYNAZAROV* (Uzbekistan)

Technical staff: **Rakhmatulla SHOKIROV** (Uzbekistan)

Prof. Dr. Rustam HALMURADOV – Ş.Raşidov adına Semerkant Devlet Üniversitesi Rektörü (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Hakim HUŞVAKTOV – Ş.Raşidov adına Semerkant Devlet Üniversitesi Araştırma ve İnovasyondan Sorumlu Rektör Yardımcısı (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Akmal AHATOV – Ş.Raşidov adına Semerkant Devlet Üniversitesi Uluslararası İşbirliğinden Sorumlu Rektör Yardımcısı (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Muslihiddin MUHİDDİNÖV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. İbodulla MİRZAYEV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Şuhrat SİROCİDDİNÖV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Suyun KARİMOV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Murodkasim ABDİYEV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Azamat PARDAYEV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Musa YULDAŞEV (Özbekistan);

Doç. Dr. Dilfuza CURAKULOVA (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Aftondil ERKİNOV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Kasimjon SODİKÖV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Muhabbat KURBANOVA (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Ali AKAR (Türkiye);

Prof. Dr. Abdusalem ARVAS (Türkiye);

Prof. Dr. Funda TOPRAK (Türkiye);

Prof. Dr. Musa Şamil YÜKSEL (Türkiye);

Prof. Dr. Timur KOCAOĞLU (ABD);

Prof. Dr. Hayrunnisa ALAN (Türkiye);

Prof. Dr. Varis ÇAKAN (Türkiye);

Prof. Dr. Almaz ÜLVİ (Azerbaycan);

Doç. Dr. Emrah YILMAZ (Türkiye);

Doç. Dr. Foziljon ŞUKUROV (Özbekistan);

Doç. Dr. Dilşod HURSAVOV (Özbekistan);

Prof. Dr. Şahnoza HUŞMURODOVA (Özbekistan);

Doç. Dr. Dinara İSLAMOVA (Özbekistan);

Doç. Dr. Feruza CUMANIYAZOVA (Özbekistan);

Doç. Dr. Istoda RASULOVA (Özbekistan);

Doç. Dr. Dilorom MUMİNOVA (Özbekistan);

Doç. Dr. Zarifa HUSANOVA (Özbekistan);

Dr. Feruza MANUKYAN (Özbekistan);

Sorumlu Editör: *Doç., Dr. Zokir BAYNAZAROV* (Özbekistan)

Teknik Personel: **Rahmatullah ŞOKIROV** (Özbekistan)

MUNDARIJA | CONTENT | İÇERİK | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ

TURKIY XALQLARNING QADIMIY TARIXI

YULDASHEV Muso, YULDASHEVA Dilshoda
TURKIYLAR UZOQ O‘TMISH SIVILIZATSIYASINING SHOHIDI (SHUMER, ETRUSK, SHIMOLIY AMERIKA HINDU VA TURKIY TILLARI QIYOSIDA).....7
SAYFULLAEV Baxtiyor, ERGASHEV Odil, UNGALOV Lazizbek
QO‘SHRABOT TUMANINING QADIMGI TOSH (PALEOLIT) DAVRI YODGORLIKLARI15

TURK DUNYOSI TADQIQOTLARI

Gulnoz SATTOROVA
RIZO NURNING ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIKKA DOIR TADQIQOTLARI.....23
Emrah YILMAZ
DİLİN İÇ YÜZÜ VE KULLANIM ALANLARI29
G‘AFFOROV Alisher
BADIIY ASAR NOMI SIFATIDA QO‘LLANAYOTGAN BIRIKMASHAKLLARNING AYRIM FUNKSIONAL-SEMANTIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....41
ODINAYEV Chingiz
TURK XOQONLIGI DAVRIDA SUG‘D VOHA HUKMDORLIGINING UNVONLAR TIZIMI47
Muhammadixon BUZRUKOV
SA‘DUDDIN MAS‘UD TAFTAZONIYNING SAMARQAND DAVLAT UNIVERSITETIDA SAQLANAYOTGAN RIYOZIYOT ILMIGA OID QO‘LYOZMA ASARI XUSUSIDA.....54
ABBOSOV Habibullo
SOHIBQIRON AMIR TEMUR MA‘NAVIY DUNYOSI ALISHER NAVOIY TALQINIDA60
SAFAYEV Mansur
TURKISTON GILAM SAN‘ATI: KOLLEKSIONERLIK VA KO‘RGAZMALAR FAOLIYATI KONTEKSTIDA.....67
ДОСПАНОВ Октябрь
ИСТОРИКО-ЭТНОГРАФИЧЕСКИЙ И КУЛЬТУРНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ТРАДИЦИОННОГО РЫБОВОДСТВА У НАРОДОВ ЮЖНОГО ПРИАРАЛЬЯ75
FURKATOVA Maxliyo
THE UZBEK ACCUSATIVE CASE IN ENGLISH: A CONTRASTIVE-TYPOLOGICAL STUDY.....83
MUXAMMADIYEV Nodir
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI O‘ZBEK SHEVALARIDAGI O‘ZLASHMA SO‘ZLAR SEMANTIKASI90
Uzm. Esra Yarız
BEDRİYE NAİM MUTLU‘NUN “BİTMEYEN HİKÂYELER” VE “AİLE AĞACI” KİTAPLARI ÜZERİNE İNCELEMELER95
Zeynep GÜLER
SEVİNÇ ÇOKUM‘UN HİLAL GÖRÜNÜNCE ROMANINDA TÜRKÇÜ TAVIRI.....102

ADABIY ALOQALAR, QIYOSIY TILSHUNOSLIK VA ADABIYOTSHUNOSLIK

SATTOROV Begzod
XITOIY VA TURKIY ADABIYOTDA KONNOTATIV NOMINATSIYA: MAQOLLAR VA SHE‘RIYAT KONTEKSTIDA TADQIQOT108
Foziljon SHUKUROV
“JAVOBIYA” AN‘ANASINING MOVAROUNNAHR SHOIRLARI IJODIDAGI O‘RNI115
BAYIMBETOVA Mexriban
THE FORMATION SYSTEM OF IMITATIVE WORDS IN THE ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES.....120
РАДЖАБОВ Анвар
РЕЦЕПЦИЯ ТЮРКО-ПЕРСИДСКОЙ ПОЭЗИИ ЧЕРЕЗ ПРИЗМУ РУССКИХ ПОЭТИЧЕСКИХ ПЕРЕВОДОВ128

AZIZ MUSHTARIY!

Ushbu sonning asosiy o'qi, tilning badiiy chuqurligi bilan tarixning qadimiy izlarini birlashtiruvchi o'ziga xos tadqiqotlardan tashkil topgan. She'riyatda til birliklarining takrori va konnotativ quvvati, Alisher Navoiyning ulug' hukmdor Amir Temurning ma'naviy dunyosiga doir sharhlari, Turk-fors she'riyatining ruscha tarjimalari ushbu yozuvning adabiyot kategoriyasidagi asosiy doirasini shakllantirgan. Shu bilan birga, Xitoy va turkiy adabiyotdagi konnotativ nominatsiya, ingliz va qoraqalpoq tillaridagi taqlid so'zlarning yasalish tizimi qiyosiy ravishda ko'rib chiqilgan. Tarix va arxeologik tadqiqotlar orqali turkiy xalqlarning qadimiy Shumer va Etrusk tillari bilan qurgan sivilizatsion aloqasiga diqqat jalb etilgan. Turk Xoqonligi davridagi Sug'd unvonlar tizimlari o'rganilgan va Qo'shrabat hududidagi Paleolit davriga oid arxeologik topilmalar vositasida madaniy merosimizning turli qatlamlari ko'z oldiga keltirilgan. Yakunda; Turkiston gilam san'atining kolleksiyonerlik kontekstidagi qadri, Samarqandda topilgan noyob matematika qo'lyozmasining muhtevosi, badiiy asarlar nomining funksional xususiyatlari, tilning ichki mohiyati va qo'llanish sohalari, Qashqadaryo shevalaridagi o'zlashma iboralarning semantikasi bilan to'ldirilgan ushbu boy to'plam, o'quvchilarga madaniy va ilmiy jihatdan turli xil istiqbollarni taqdim etmoqda.

TAHRIRIYAT

DEAR READER!

The central axis of this issue consists of original research that integrates the artistic depth of language with the ancient traces of history. The recurrence and connotative power of linguistic units in poetry, Alisher Navoi's commentaries on the spiritual world of the great ruler Amir Timur, and the reception of Turco-Persian poetry through Russian translations have formed the core framework for the literature category of this writing. Furthermore, connotative nomination in Chinese and Turkic literature, and the word-formation system of imitative words in the English and Karakalpak languages have been comparatively addressed. Through historical and archaeological studies, attention has been drawn to the civilizational connection established by the Turkic peoples with the ancient Sumerian and Etruscan languages. The titles of the Sogdian rulers during the Turkic Khaganate period have been examined, and various layers of our cultural heritage have been brought to light through Paleolithic archaeological findings in the Qushrabad region. Finally; this rich compilation, completed with the value of Turkestan carpet art in the context of connoisseurship, the content of a rare mathematics manuscript found in Samarkand, the functional characteristics of artistic work titles, the inner essence and areas of use of language, and the semantics of non-literal expressions in the Kashkadarya dialects, offers various perspectives to readers from a cultural and scientific standpoint.

EDITORIAL BOARD

SEVGİLİ OKUYUCU!

Bu sayının ana eksenini, dilin sanatsal derinligi ile tarixning kadim izlarini birlestiren o'zgün araştırmalardan oluşmaktadır. Şiirde dil birliklerinin tekrarı ve çağrışımsal gücü, Alî Şîr Nevâî'nin büyük hükümdar Emir Timur'un manevi dünyasına dair yorumları, Türk-Fars şiirinin Rusça çevirileri konuları yazının edebiyat kategorisindeki temel çerçevesini oluşturmuştur. Bununla birlikte Çin ve Türk edebiyatındaki konnotatif adlandırma, İngilizce ve Karakalpakça'daki yansıma sözcüklerin yapısı karşılaştırmalı olarak ele alınmıştır. Tarih ve arkeoloji çalışmaları üzerinden Türklerin kadim Sümer ve Etrusk dilleriyle kurduğu medeniyet bağlantısına dikkat çekilmiştir. Türk Kağanlığı dönemindeki Soğd unvan sistemleri incelenmiş ve Kuşrabad bölgesindeki Paleolitik döneme ait arkeolojik bulgular aracılığıyla kültürel mirasımızın farklı katmanları gözler önüne serilmiştir. Son olarak; Türkistan kilim sanatının koleksiyonerlik bağlamındaki değeri, Semerkant'ta bulunan nadir bir matematik el yazmasının muhtevası, bediî eserlerin işlevsel özellikleri, dilin iç yüzü ve kullanım alanları, Kaşkaderya ağızlarındaki dolaylı anlatımların semantiği ile tamamlanan bu zengin seçki, okuyuculara kültürel ve bilimsel açıdan farklı perspektifler sunmaktadır.

YAYIN KURULU

УВАЖАЕМЫЙ ЧИТАТЕЛЬ!

Основу данного выпуска составляют оригинальные исследования, которые объединяют художественную глубину языка с древними страницами истории. В разделе поэзии рассматриваются повторяемость и коннотативная сила языковых единиц; представлены комментарии Алишера Навои, посвящённые духовному миру великого правителя Амира Темура; а также анализируются русские переводы тюрко-персидской поэзии, формирующие основное направление литературной категории этого номера. В сравнительном аспекте анализируются коннотативная номинация в китайской и тюркской литературе, а также система словообразования звукоподражательных слов в английском и каракалпакском языках. Посредством исторических и археологических исследований обращается внимание на цивилизационные связи тюркских народов с древними шумерским и этрусским языками. Изучены системы согдийских титулов периода Тюркского каганата, а археологические находки палеолитического периода, обнаруженные на территории Кушрабадского региона, позволяют реконструировать различные пласты нашего культурного наследия. В заключение, этот обширный сборник, дополненный исследованиями о ценности туркестанского коврового искусства в контексте коллекционирования, содержании уникальной математической рукописи, найденной в Самарканде, функциональных особенностей наименований художественных произведений, внутренней сущности и сферах употребления языка, а также семантике заимствованных выражений в кашкадарьинских говорах, предлагает читателям широкий спектр культурных и научных перспектив.

РЕДАКЦИОННАЯ КОЛЛЕГИИ

THE FORMATION OF ONOMATOPOEIC WORDS IN THE ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

BAYIMBETOVA Mexriban Berdibaevna,

Ingliz tili va adabiyoti kafedrası assistent-o‘qituvchi,

Nukus davlat pedagogika instituti

(Nukus, Qoraqalpog‘iston)

E-mail: bayimbetovam@mail.ru

 ORCID: 0009-0009-9196-7121

 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17498846>

Abstract: This scientific article examines the methods of forming other parts of speech from imitative words in the Karakalpak and English languages through conversion and affixation. The main objective of the research is to identify the similarities and differences in the morphological structures of both languages when creating new parts of speech from imitative words. To achieve this goal, the study employs a comparative-typological approach, allowing for a systematic analysis of the similarities and differences in the word-formation systems of English and Karakalpak. Special attention is given to how the processes of affixation and conversion alter the grammatical features of imitative words, providing insight into the general mechanisms of language evolution and structural development. By examining these trends, the study paves the way for a deeper understanding of how universal and language-specific factors influence the emergence and development of imitative words in each language.

Key words: *Conversion, affix, imitative word, onomatopoeia, morphology, the Karakalpak language, derivative.*

INGLIZ VA QORAQALPOQ TILLARIDA TAQLID SO‘ZLARNING YASALISHI

Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqolada qoraqalpoq va ingliz tillaridagi taqlid so‘zlardan konversiya va affiksatsiya orqali boshqa so‘z turkumlarini hosil qilish usullari o‘rganilgan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi taqlid so‘zlardan yangi so‘z turkumlarini hosil qilishda har ikki tilning morfologik tuzilishidagi o‘xshash va farqli jihatlarni aniqlashdan iborat. Ushbu maqsadga erishish uchun tadqiqotda ingliz va qoraqalpoq tillaridagi so‘z yasash tizimlarining o‘xshash va farqli jihatlarni tizimli o‘rganish imkonini beruvchi qiyosiy-tipologik yondashuv qo‘llaniladi. Affiksatsiya va konversiya jarayonlari taqlid so‘zlarning grammatik xususiyatlarini qanday o‘zgartirishiga alohida e‘tibor qaratiladi, bu esa til evolyutsiyasi va tarkibiy rivojlanishining umumiy mexanizmlari haqida tasavvur beradi. Ushbu tendensiyalarni ko‘rib chiqish orqali tadqiqot taqlid so‘zlarning paydo bo‘lishi va rivojlanishiga har bir til uchun universal va o‘ziga xos omillar qanday ta‘sir ko‘rsatishini chuqurroq tushunishga yo‘l ochadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *konversiya, affiks, taqlid so‘z, onomatopiya, morfologiya, qoraqalpoq tili, yasama so‘z.*

СЛОВООБРАЗОВАНИЕ ЗВУКОПОДРАЖАТЕЛЬНЫХ СЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И КАРАКАЛПАКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация: В данной научной статье исследуются способы образования других частей речи из звукоподражательных слов в каракалпакском и английском языках посредством конверсии и аффиксации. Основная цель исследования заключается в выявлении сходств и различий в морфологической структуре обоих языков при образовании новых частей речи из звукоподражательных слов. Для достижения этой цели

в исследовании применяется сравнительно-типологический подход, который позволяет систематически изучать сходства и различия словообразовательных систем в английском и каракалпакском языках. Особое внимание уделяется тому, как процессы аффиксации и конверсии изменяют грамматические свойства звукоподражательных слов, что дает представление об общих механизмах эволюции и структурного развития языка. Рассматривая эти тенденции, исследование открывает путь к более глубокому пониманию того, как универсальные и специфические для каждого языка факторы влияют на возникновение и развитие подражательных слов.

Ключевые слова: *конверсия, аффикс, подражательное слово, ономотопея, морфология, каракалпакский язык, производное слово.*

Introduction. English and Karakalpak languages have different ways of word formation. One of them is conversion, where a word in one part of speech changes into another part of speech and changes its meaning. Regardless of the method or means of word formation, new vocabulary is considered the creation of meaningful words.

In linguistics, the concept of conversion is the connection between the boundaries of morphology and syntax. Research in literary studies provides us with various observations. However, none of these can serve as the sole solution or sufficient explanation for how this process will unfold. Nevertheless, each theory has its own specific basis. Based on these principles, we can study the concept of conversion and analyze it. We can even implement the possible changes. The key characteristic of this morphological or syntactic process is that it undergoes changes in its constituent words related to the lexical category.

The statement that “Words unite and form according to the grammatical laws of a particular language in speech” once again confirms the strong connection between lexicology and grammar (Arnold 2012:19).

Methods. This study examines onomatopoeic word construction in Karakalpak and English using a comparative linguistic method, with an emphasis on affixation and conversion.

In terms of conversion, the study analyzes the syntactic functions and contextual usage of imitative words, examining how they function as distinct parts of speech without undergoing morphological modifications.

By contrasting structural patterns in the two languages, it investigates how prefixes and suffixes alter meaning and grammatical category in relation to affixation.

This method guarantees a methodical analysis of the grammatical functions of imitative words in both languages.

Results. V.Ya.Plotkin, in characterizing the structure of the English language, generally observes “a radical typological restructuring that has unfolded in English, transforming it from an inflectional, synthetic language into an analytical one, combining in its structure the properties of both a root-isolating and an agglutinative language” (Plotkin 1989: 229).

According to E. S. Kubryakova, the productivity and activity of word formation models depend not only on intralinguistic but also on extralinguistic data: 1) the volume and speed of expansion of conceptual categories corresponding to a certain type of word formation, and 2) the number of words serves as the basis for derivation [Kubryakova 1965:18,20]. In other words, the potential scope of a word-formation series depends on the actual correlation of a specific model with the concrete world of objects, concepts, and relationships. E.S. Kubryakova further notes that “the creation of members of a particular word-formation series can be hindered by phonetic

factors, i.e., the sound incompatibility of individual components of the derived word, and morphological factors, particularly the morphological structure of bases that combine with other bases or affixes” (Kubryakova 1965:18, 20).

At the same time, the productivity/non-productivity of affixes should not be confused with their frequency of use. Even non-productive affixes can be commonly used (Arnold 2012: 125, 126).

Muhammad Barru Siddiq examines the categories of word groups for each onomatopoeic word found in the comic book “Halk”. The writer focuses on some types of parts of speech namely nouns, verbs, and interjections (Siddiq 2019:106). In his analysis, he states: “Just as every word has its own word groups, onomatopoeia also has them. According to Vilma Kokko's thesis, she demonstrated that Kaindl (1999:273-274) divided onomatopoeia into three-word groups (Kokko 2017:37), (Kaindl 1999:263-288). These are interjections, nouns, and verbs. Imitative words, depending on their usage, can function as sound effects, interjections, nouns, and verbs, depending on how they express a particular event or action. For example, the word “thump”, when used in the noun form, means “a heavy blow”, and when used in the verb form, it means “to strike”, “to hit”, or expresses the meaning of “a hard object being struck” (Siddiq 2019:106).

Moreover, scientists study onomatopoeia in English based on several factors:

1) They rarely take suffixes in English compared to other languages. In English, onomatopoeia is mainly mono-syllable, rarely two or three-syllable. For example: *ding, flap, gulp, hark, hush, bang, twinkle, thunder, jingle*;

2) The high productivity of word formation contributes to the easy conversion (modification) of onomatopoeia from one part of speech to another within a sentence. For example: *to hiss* (verb), *hiss* (noun), *to ding* (verb), *ding* (noun).

Onomatopoeia belongs to a specific group of word branches based on their meaning, morphological properties, and syntactic functions. According to T.Sugahara, onomatopoeia in English can be used as nouns, verbs, adverbs and interjections (Sugahara 2010:17). For example:

- a. His heavy boots **clatter** upon the round pebbles. (Verb)
- b. The **chug** of the engine still filled our ears. (Noun)
- c. The carriage went **bump, bump, bump** over the sleepers. (Adverb)
- d. This **flabby** lump of mortality. (Adjective)
- e. **Whirr!** The exploded cork whizzed through the air. (Interjection)

Also, the same word can also be used as a different part of speech. For example:

- a. The cannons’ **booms** startled them. (Noun)
- b. The cannons **boomed** incessantly. (Verb)
- c. The dogs’ **arfs** began to bother everyone. (Noun)
- d. The dogs continued to **arf**. (Verb)

In the Karakalpak language, onomatopoeic words play a significant role in grammar in creating new words through various methods. Therefore, the meanings of onomatopoeic words can be understood from the context. While onomatopoeic words are close to idioms in terms of intonation, they are not similar to interjections in terms of word formation.

Particularly nouns, adjectives, and verbs are formed from imitative words through several methods. Onomatopoeia itself is not formed from other parts of speech. These characteristics distinguish onomatopoeic words from other parts of speech. If we look at the examples of onomatopoeia, we can see that they are used within a sentence in the function of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. For example:

1. (a) **Ġawırılı** kem-kem kúsheydi. (noun)
(b) Balalar qońıraw shalıńıwdan birden **ġawırlastı**. (verb)
2. (a) Alıslardan ġazlardıń **ġańqıldısı** esitildi. (noun)
(b) Ele nesin kóripseń, qıl taqqan soń **ġańqıldaydı**. (verb)
- 3.(a) Júyrikten júyrik shıqsa ayaqları **tıpır-tıpır**. (adjective)
(b) Balalar ġarrını kóriwden **tıpırlap** qashtı. (adverb)

Imitative words words “**ġawırılı**” in the example of line 1 (a) and “**ġańqıldı**” in the example of line 2 (a) function as nouns. The same onomatopoeic words in the examples of the 1st line (b) and the 2nd line (b) are verbs, imitative word “**tıpırlaw**” in the 3rd line (a) example is an adjective and (b) example is an adverb.

Imitative words expressing general meaning are divided into two categories. Words belonging to the first group express only the sound produced by one object (for example, the word “**sirt**”(crack) does not express the sound produced by other objects when a tree leaf is plucked), while words belonging to the second group generally express the sound produced by several different objects. Some imitative words are used in the same form. For example: Ol **jalt-jalt** qaradı. (Adverb) Ot **jalt-jalt** etti. (Verb)

Thus, conversion, a method of word formation in English and Karakalpak, holds a prominent place in linguistics as an interaction between morphology and syntax. Through this process, words move from one branch of speech to another and form new meanings. Imitative words/onomatopoeia are connected to a new category through conversion and are used in other parts of speech, becoming increasingly grammatically rich. Not only in various parts of speech in the English language, but also in the Karakalpak language, word formation methods encompass certain morphological and general characteristics.

Another way of forming imitative words in English and Karakalpak languages is affixation. Similarly, in the Karakalpak language, affixes are used to derive other parts of speech from onomatopoeic words. An affix is a morpheme that is attached to the root of a word. Using affixes, nouns, adjectives, verbs, and adverbs can be formed from onomatopoeic words.

Noun. In English noun-forming suffixes encompass abstract and concrete nouns, as well as nouns derived from verbs and adjectives. For abstract nouns, suffixes such as **-age, -dom, -ery/-ry, -ful, -hood, -ing** are used. Concrete nouns are formed using the suffixes **-eer, -er, -ess, -ette**. Abstract nouns from verbs are created with the suffixes **-age, -al, -ation, -ing, -ment**, while person-related nouns are formed with **-ant, -ee, -er, -or**. Abstract nouns from adjectives are formed with the suffixes **-ity, -ness: chattiness** “ġápke sheshen”, **hoarseness** “qırıldaw”, **hollowness** “boslıq, gúwildi”, **babblement** “ġawırılı”, **bubbly** “shampan, kóbik”, **whammy** “kúshli zarba”, **whinny** “quwanıştan áste qıyırırw” (Smirnitskiy 1956).

As a result of studying the collected materials on the Karakalpak language, when imitative words function as nouns using the morphological method, they acquire various affixes.

1. The morphological method is considered the most active and effective method in creating words from imitative words. There are many affixes for forming other parts of speech from imitative words. They are divided into groups:

- a) affixes attached to root imitative words;
- b) affixes that attach to other forms of imitative words, substantivizing them (Embergenov 1990:49).

In the Karakalpak language, the affixes **- a, - ı, - e, - ıq, - na, - maq, -paq, - ġısh, - ama, - mama, - il-il, - ılı, - li** are among the productive affixes in the formation of nouns from imitative

words. When these affixes are often added to two-syllable onomatopoeic words, they substantivize the onomatopoeic words. For example: *saqa, taqa, sholpi, dúńke, shijiq, tırna, shaqmaq, toppaq, qurǵısh, sıldrama, guldirmama, tarsıl, gúrsıl, patur, gútır, tasırlı, dúsirli*, h.t.b.

Verb. Verbs derived from onomatopoeia are practically present in English, for example, words used as verbs like “**thwack**”, “**jingle**”, “**twinkle**” constitute a very large number. Verbs are classified as one of three main groups according to how they express processes. Firstly, they represent action. Secondly, they can illustrate events, and finally, they are used to convey information (Morley, 2000:33).

The main morphological forms of the verb in modern English include the infinitive, the indefinite past tense, and the adjective. If it has the same morphological characteristics in onomatopoeia, it is used as a verb. For example:

- 1) Infinitive: *The bee has **to** buzz.*
- 2) Past Simple: *The bee **buzzed**.*
- 3) Present Participle: *The **buzzing** bee was flying around the room.*
- 4) Past participle: *The **buzzed** bee flew out the door.*

Furthermore, imitative words can also be used as gerunds. A gerund is formed by adding the suffix “**-ing**” to the verb root. The gerund has the same form as present participle (Sugahara 2010:113). For example:

- The **cawing** of a crow...*
*The **twinkling** of the lights...*

N.A.Baskakov discusses the morphological formation of verbs from Karakalpak imitative words and identifies the connections of several affixes (Baskakov 1952:249-250). When verbs are formed from imitative words using the morphological method, various affixes are attached to imitative words (especially to root and derived root onomatopoeic words), for example, the affixes **-ra, -re, -la, -le** are attached to onomatopoeic words ending in **-ır, -ir**. In addition to these, N.A. Baskakov indicates that affixes like **-lak -lek, -daq -dek, -law -lew, -raw -rew, -dawıq -dewik** are actively attached to onomatopoeic words, thereby forming verbs (Baskakov 1952:253).

Verbs formed by affixation from imitative words possess all the grammatical features characteristic of base verbs and they are formed in all three tenses. For example: 1. Kóldegi ǵazlar, úyrekler **ǵańqıldadı** (K. Sultanov). – Past tense. 2. Onıń murnınan aqshıl, qara tútin **burqırmaqta** (Q. Dosanov) – Present tense. 3. Ele nesin kóripseń, qıl taqqan soń **ǵańqıldaydı** (proverb) – Future tense.

Adjective. In English, adjectives have three degrees of comparison: positive, comparative, and superlative. The positive degree represents the basic form of the adjective (tall, small, beautiful), the comparative degree indicates a higher level of quality (taller, smaller, more beautiful), and the superlative degree expresses the highest level of quality (tallest, smallest, most beautiful). As a rule, adjectives typically end with suffixes such as **-y, -ow, -er, -le**, but many adjectives derived from participles end with the suffixes **-ed or -ing**.

- 1) Positive degree: Carmen pulled the **crisp** drawer out.
- 2) Comparative degree: Carmen pulled the **crisper** drawer out.
- 3) Superlative degree: Carmen pulled **the crispest** drawer out.

The Karakalpak language is rich in adjective-modifying affixes. Adjectives are mainly formed by adding affixes to the following derived and basic types of imitative words:

1. Affixes attached to verbs derived from imitative words: **jıtır-a-q, salpıl-da-q, gúmpıl-de-k, elpıl-de-k, jıtır-aw-ıq, gúrkirew-ik, gumbirle-gish**.

2. Affixes attached to nouns derived from imitative words: **sırıl-daq, girtıl-dek, sıqlı-daq, gúril-dek, jıl- pıl-daq.**

3. Affixes attached to words whose roots are imitators: **salp-ı, sar-ı, jalp-aq, tısrılı.**

Adverb. Despite the small number of adverbial modifier affixes in English, they are effectively used in literary works to describe the states and inner feelings of characters. According to their morphological structure, adverbs are typically classified as follows: simple adverbs, derivative adverbs, complex adverbs, and compound adverbs. Although adverbs also have degrees of comparison, they are often not used when they function as imitations.

When onomatopoeic words are used as adverbs, they typically function as simple adverbs and are almost never used as derived or compound adverbs. The role of an adverb is to modify a verb or adjective. Therefore, when an onomatopoeic word is used as an adverb in a sentence, its identification is very clear [Sugahara 2010:39].

For example: 1) Simple: *My ice-cream fell **splat** onto the pavement. (Muzqaymağım tratuarğa bulsh etip tústi)*

2) Complex: *Rain fell **pitter-patter** against the windowpane (Jawın aynağa qaray patırlap quydı).*

The formation of adverbs from imitative words has not been systematically defined in the Karakalpak language, similar to other Turkic languages. In some scholarly works, words like **sharta, tarsa, shorta** are presented as adverbs derived from imitative words. However, such words are considered adverbs in other Turkic languages as well. In some Turkic languages, it is stated that adverbs are formed from imitative words, while in others, this topic is not addressed. For instance, S.Khudaybergenov and M.Khudaykuliev, in their specialized research, do not indicate the formation of adverbs from imitative words (Khudaybergenov 1957:16), (Khudaykuliev 1962:44). A.Isxakov, in his works on adverbs and imitative words, demonstrates that adverbs are derived from onomatopoeic words and that this is an active form (Isxakov 1959:37), (Isxakov 1951:111).

In the Karakalpak language, the -a affix, which forms adverbs from onomatopoeic words, is considered the most productive. This affix, attached to a monosyllabic sound imitation word, creates an adverb indicating the speed of the action: **tars-a, shar-ta, sharp-a, short-a, etc.**

The unproductive affix - **pa** forms an adverb when attached to certain imitative words. For example: **lap-pa**. Words with these affixes can only be used in reduplicative way (lap-lap) without conveying a figurative meaning.

Outwardly, some onomatopoeic words appear similar to interjections, but they differ in that they express neither feelings nor volition. Onomatopoeic words are used as an expressive-stylistic means of depicting reality: bow-wow - imitating a dog's bark; cuckoo-cuckoo! - imitating a cuckoo's call.

Taking into account the various emotional and physical states a person can experience, it would be appropriate and logical to distinguish the following subgroups of imitative interjections of a genuine interjective nature: (Djamshedov 2002:58).

I. Blowing with the mouth. Imitative sounds of this kind can arise by mimicking the strong exhalation produced by a person as a result of fatigue, intense physical exertion, after running fast, feeling relief from an unexpected danger, and so on.

For example:

Hoop! - exhalation produced by a person as a result of extreme fatigue;

Phew! - exhalation made by a person as a result of unexpected relief from danger, facilitating physical relaxation after lifting a heavy weight, etc.

A distinctive feature of this group is the presence of consonants **r**, **h**, and **ph** in the composition of imitative words. These consonants are pronounced with strong aspiration, thereby mimicking a forceful exhalation.

II. Dissatisfied exhalation. This group of sound images is close to first group, both in terms of execution technique and individual sounds comprising them.

Indeed, the mechanisms for reproducing sounds in both groups are very similar, differing only in the external or internal reasons that prompt a person to produce such sounds.

Thus, the following units can be attributed to this group of internal onomatopoeias of the interjection type:

“Posh!” - a sound expressing a contemptuous attitude towards something or someone; “Pish!” - a sound indicating disgust or contempt experienced by the person uttering it.

Once again, we can identify characteristic features of the imitative words in this group. These onomatopoeias are distinguished by the hissing consonant sounds '**p**' and '**sh**', pronounced with a strong aspiration.

III. Exhalation in surprise, pain, admiration, joy.

Charles Darwin characterized the sound imitation of this group as follows:

“When something strongly strikes us or we are inevitably surprised by something, we immediately show a tendency to open our mouth wide to take a deep and quick inhalation. When complete exhalation follows, the mouth slightly closes, and the lips protrude slightly. With such a mouth shape, the sound produced will sound like the vowel o \ oh\.. If the feeling of surprise is accompanied by pain, there is a tendency for facial muscles to contract: and in this case, the lips are pulled back, consequently, the sound becomes higher and is heard as A!\ Ah!” (Voronin 1989:651).

Thus, in English, we found the following examples:

Oho! - Wow! - an exclamation expressing surprise;

Ah! - Oh! - an exclamation capable of denoting, depending on the situation: delight, surprise, unexpectedness, or pain;

Oh! - an exclamation characterizing a person's surprised (or excited) state.

All the above-mentioned subgroups belong to a relatively small genetic category of interjection imitatives. Despite their relatively small number, sound imitations of this kind are extremely important for communication.

However, it should be noted that we did not find such a classification of interjection-like imitative words in the Karakalpak language.

Thus, we have examined a significant group of imitative words that mimic sounds produced by the human speech apparatus, belonging to the genetic category of internal sound representations.

This group of imitative words reflects the sound processes that a person uses in communication. As a rule, these sounds (processes) occur unintentionally, and as interjection-like imitatives, they are natural, as they reproduce rather than imitate certain sound combinations. One can also speak of a certain degree of unintentionality in the emergence of imitative words of this type, but in such cases, it is most likely pure imitation, rather than a reflection of sound processes occurring involuntarily and necessarily.

Conclusion

In conclusion, particular difference of forming parts of speech from imitative words between two languages is that in the English language a noun, a verb, an adjective, an adverb, and an interjection are formed and in the Karakalpak language also a noun, a verb, an adjective, and an adverb are formed excluding an interjection.

These parts of speech are used equally in both English and Karakalpak by conversion. Similarly, in both English and Karakalpak, the conversion of imitative words into other parts of speech can occur with and without affixes. This indicates that imitative words not only a separate part of speech but can also change freely in other parts of speech, and the formation of parts of speech from imitative words is equally present in the English and Karakalpak language systems.

Iqtiboslar/ References/ Kaynaklar/ Сноски:

1. Арнольд И.В. (2012) Лексикология современного английского языка. Учебное пособие 2-е издание, переработанное. Москва Издательство «ФЛИНТА» Издательство «Наука». – С.19.
2. Баскаков Н.А. (1952) Каракалпакский язык II Фонетика и морфология. Часть I. Части речи. Москва. – С.239.
3. Воронин С.В. (1989) Из инструментария фоносемасиолога: модель и фоне-мотип//Контекстуально-обусловленная вариативность единиц языка.- Рига.-С.651.
4. Джемшедов П.Д. (2002) Имитативы в современном английском языке,- Душанбе, - С. 51.
5. Ембергенов У. (1990) Хэзирги қарақалпақ тилиндеги еликлеўиш сөзлер. –Нөкис: «Қарақалпақстан». – 17 б. (In Karakalpak)
6. Исаков, А. И. (1951) О подражательных словах в казахском языке. «Тюркологический сборник», №1, М. –Л.– С.111.
7. Исхаков, А. И. (1959) Наречие в современном Казахском языке, Алма-Ата. - С. 37.
8. Кубрякова, Е.С. (1965) Что такое словообразование . –М.: Изд-во «Наука». – С. 18, 20.
9. Кудайбергенов С. (1957) Подражательные слова в киргизском языке. Фрунзе. – С.16.
10. Плоткин, В.Я. (1989) Строй английского языка. Учеб. пособие для ин-тов и фак. иностр. яз. – М.: Высш. шк. – С.239. (In Russian)
11. Смирницкий, А.И. (1956) Лексикология английского языка. – М.
12. Худайкулиев, М. (1962) Подражательные слова в туркменском языке, Ашхабад. – С.36.
13. Kaindl, C. (1999) Thump, whizz, boom: A framework for the study of comics under translation. *Target 11*(2). – 263-288 pp.
14. Kokko, V. (2017) *KPOW, CHINK, SPLAT: Translation of sound effects in seven comics*. (Master’s thesis). University of Turku, Turku.
15. Morley, D. (2004) *Syntax in functional grammar: An introduction to lexicogrammar in systemic linguistics*. Newyork: British Library. Oxford: Blackwell Publishing, – 2nd ed. – 59-71pp.
16. Siddiq, M.B. (2019) Onomatopoeia and word class categories analysis in Hulk digital comic, Annual International Conference (AIC). – 102 p.
17. Sugahara, T. (2010) Onomatopoeia in Spoken and Written English : Corpus- and Usage-based Analysis. Hokkaido University Collection of Scholarly and Academic Papers : HUSCAP . Dissertation paper. – 17 p.

**BULLETIN OF THE
INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL
“TURKOLOGICAL
RESEARCH”**

In order to implement programs and projects developed to accelerate the relationship envisaged at the summit of the Organization of Turkic States held in Samarkand, as well as to coordinate and highlight the research work carried out in the field of Turkic studies, the International Journal “Turkological Research” at Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov passed the state registration. The journal is intended to publish the results of scientific research in the field of Turkic languages and dialects, the history of linguistic and literary relations of the Turkic peoples of Central Asia, the socio-cultural field. There are such headings as a young researcher, memory and our anniversaries. Articles written in Uzbek, Turkish, Russian, English and all Turkic languages are accepted.

The scientific journal is based on the decision of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 8, 2024 and numbered 354/5; It is included in the list of scientific publications that are recommended for candidates to receive the Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) and Doctor of Science (DSc) academic degrees in the fields of history and philology to publish their scientific results due to their theses.

**THE JOURNAL PUBLISHES ARTICLES
IN THE FOLLOWING AREAS:**

- ✓ History of socio-cultural relations of the Turkic peoples;
- ✓ Research of the Turkic World;
- ✓ Dialectology of Turkic languages;
- ✓ Geopolitics of the Turkic World;
- ✓ Folklore Studies;
- ✓ Comparative Linguistics and Literary Studies;
- ✓ Literary Relations and Translation Studies.

CONTACT ADDRESS:

Mailing Address:

140104, University boulevard, 15,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan,
Research Institute of Turkology under
Samarkand State University named after
Sharof Rashidov

Phone:

+998 91 527 68 22

+998 99 596 35 69

+998 97 911 93 81

Telegram ID:

@turkologiya2025

Email:

turkologiya.samdu@gmail.com

Website:

<https://turkologiya.samdu.uz>

REQUIREMENTS FOR ARTICLES:

- The article is presented on 8-10 pages;
- Article structure:
 1. The text of the article should be prepared in Times News Roman font, size 14, left: 3 cm, right: 1.5 cm, top and bottom: 2 cm; in A4 format in 1.15 intervals.
 2. The title of the article, surname, name and patronymic of the author (authors) are indicated in full and written in capital letters.
 3. Position, academic title, place of work (study), region, republic, telephone number, email address and ORCID number of the author (authors) are indicated in full.
 4. The abstract should consist of a brief content and importance of the article, results.
 5. At the beginning of each article, there should be an annotation in 2 other languages (optionally selected from Uzbek, English, Russian and Turkish) in addition to the language in which the article is written.
 6. The abstract should be no more than 120-150 words.
 7. At the bottom of the abstract, 7-10 keywords should be given that illuminate the content of the article.
 8. The article should be prepared in the following form:
 - a) Introduction;
 - b) Main part;
 - c) Results and Discussions;
 - d) Conclusions;
 - e) List of literature (References) – in alphabetical order;
 - f) Citations are given in brackets in the form of the author's surname - date of publication - page (Muminov, 2020: 25);
 - g) Figures, drawings, tables, diagrams are designated in Arabic numerals as "Figure". Signs or pointers are placed under the figure, in the next line, in the middle and highlighted in bold.
- The topic of the scientific article submitted by the author (or co-authors) must correspond to the journal's columns.
- Articles can be submitted in Uzbek, English, Russian, and all other Turkic languages
- The author(s) are responsible for the scientific validity, reliability and plagiarism of the information and evidence presented in the article;
- Articles will be considered. The journal publishes only articles recommended by experts;
- Articles not requested will not be published and will not be returned to the authors;
- Only 1 article of the author is published in 1 issue of the journal.

“TURKOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR” XALQARO JURNALINING AXBOROT XATI

Davlatimiz tomonidan olib borilayotgan ijtimoiy-ma’rifiy, ilm-fanni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan siyosat, Turkiy Davlatlar Tashkilotining Samarqanda o‘tkazilgan sammitida ko‘zda tutilgan o‘zaro aloqalarni jadallashtirish bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan dastur va loyihalarni amalga oshirish hamda turkologiya sohasida olib borilayotgan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarini muvofiqlashtirish va yoritish maqsadida Sharof Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand davlat universitetida “Turkologik tadqiqotlar” xalqaro jurnali ta’sis etildi. Jurnal turkiy til va shevalar, Markaziy Osiyo turkiy xalqlari lisoniy va adabiy aloqalari tarixi, ijtimoiy-madaniy sohalarda amalga oshirilayotgan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlarining natijalarini e’lon qilishga mo’ljallangan. Jurnalda muharrir minbari, tadqiqotlar, ilmiy axborot, taqriz va e’tirof, ilmiy anjuman, yosh tadqiqotchi, xotira, yubilyarlarimiz kabi ruknlar mavjud. O‘zbek, turk, rus, ingliz va barcha turkiy tillarda yozilgan maqolalar qabul qilinadi.

Ilmiy jurnal O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi OAKning 2024-yil 8-maydagi 354/5-sonli rayosat qarori asosida tarix, filologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) va fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiya ishlari yuzasidan dissertatsiyalari asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etish tavsiya etilgan ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan.

JURNAL QUIYIDAGI YO‘NALISHLARDAGI MAQOLALARNI NASHR QILADI:

- ✓ Turkiy xalqlarning ijtimoiy-madaniy aloqalari tarixi
- ✓ Turk dunyosi tadqiqotlari
- ✓ Turkiy tillar dialektologiya
- ✓ Folklorshunoslik
- ✓ Qiyosiy tilshunoslik va adabiyotshunoshlik
- ✓ Adabiy aloqalar va tarjimashunoslik.

MUROJAAT UCHUN MANZIL:

Pochta manzili:

140104, Universitet xiyoboni, 15-uy,
Samarqand, O‘zbekiston,
Sharof Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand
davlat universiteti huzuridagi
Turkologiya ilmiy-tadqiqot instituti

Telefon:

+998 91 527 68 22

+998 99 596 35 69

+998 97 911 93 81

Telegram ID:

@turkologiya2025

Elektron pochta:

turkologiya.samdu@gmail.com

Veb-sayt:

<https://turkologiya.samdu.uz>

MAQOLALARGA QO‘YILADIGAN TALABLAR:

- Maqola 8-10 sahifa hajmida taqdim etiladi;
- Maqolaning tarkibiy tuzilishi:
- 1. Maqola matni Times News Roman shriftida, 14 kattalikda, chap: 3 sm, o‘ng: 1,5 sm, yuqori va quyi: 2 sm; 1,5 intervalda, A4 shaklida tayyorlanishi lozim.
- 2. Maqola sarlavhasi, muallif(lar)ning familiyasi, ismi va otasmi to‘liq holatda katta harflar bilan yozilishi kerak.
- 3. Muallif(lar)ning lavozimi, ilmiy unvoni, ish (o‘qish) joylari, viloyat, Respublika, telefon raqami, elektron pochta manzili va ORCID raqqami to‘liq keltirilishi kerak.
- 4. Annotatsiya, maqolaning qisqacha mazmun va ahamiyati, natijalardan iborat bo‘lishi lozim.
- 5. Har bir maqola boshida maqola yozilgan tildan tashqari yana 2 tilda (o‘zbek, ingliz, rus va turk tillaridan ixtiyoriy ravishda tanlanadi) annotatsiya bo‘lishi lozim.
- 6. Annotatsiya 120-150 so‘zdan ko‘p bo‘lmagan shaklda bo‘lishi kerak.
- 7. Annotatsiyaning pastki qismida maqola mazmunini yorituvchi 7-10 ta tayanch so‘zlar keltirilishi kerak.
- 8. Maqola quyidagi shaklda tayyorlanishi kerak:
 - a) Kirish (Introduction);
 - b) Asosiy qism (Main part);
 - c) Natijalar va muhokama (Results and Discussions);
 - d) Xulosalar (Conclusions);
 - e) Adabiyotlar (References) – alifbo tartibida keltiriladi;
 - f) Havola(snoskalar)lar qavsda muallif familiyasi – nashr sanasi – sahifasi (Mo‘minov, 2020: 25) shaklida keltiriladi;
 - g) Rasm, chizma, jadval, diagrammalar «Rasm» deb arab raqamlari bilan qayd etiladi. Belgi yoki ishoralar – rasm ostida, keyingi qatorda, o‘rtada joylashtiriladi va qoraytirilgan shrift bilan belgilanadi.
- Muallif (yoki hammualliflar) tomonidan taqdim etilayotgan ilmiy maqola mavzusi jurnal ruknlariga mos kelishi shart.
- Maqolalar o‘zbek, ingliz, rus va barcha turkiy tillarda taqdim etilishi mumkin.
- Maqolada keltirilgan ma’lumot va dalillarning ilmiy asoslanganligi, ishonchli va ko‘chirmachilik holatlari uchun muallif(lar) mas’uldir;
- Maqolalar ekspertiza qilinadi. Ekspertlar tomonidan tavsiya etilgan maqolalargina jurnalda chop etiladi;
- Tavsiya etilmagan maqolalar chop etilmaydi va mualliflarga qaytarilmaydi;
- Jurnalning 1 ta sonida muallifning faqat 1 ta maqolasi chop etiladi.

**БЮЛЕТЕНЬ
МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ЖУРНАЛА
"ТЮРКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ"**

В целях реализации программ и проектов, разработанных для ускорения взаимоотношений, предусмотренных на состоявшемся в Самарканде саммите Организации Тюркских Государств, а также координации и освещения научно-исследовательской работы, проводимой в области тюркологии, Международный журнал Самаркандского государственного университета имени Шарофа Рашидова «Тюркологические исследования» прошел государственную регистрацию. Журнал предназначен для публикации результатов научно-исследовательских работ в области тюркских языков и диалектов, истории языковых и литературных связей тюркских народов Средней Азии, социокультурной области. Есть такие рубрики, как молодой исследователь, память и наши юбилеи. Принимаются статьи, написанные на узбекском, турецком, русском, английском и всех тюркских языках.

Научный журнал на основании решения Высшей аттестационной комиссии (ВАК) Министерства высшего образования, науки и инноваций Республики Узбекистан от 8 мая 2024 года под номером 354/5; Он включен в перечень научных изданий, рекомендуемых кандидатам на получение ученых степеней доктора философии (PhD) и доктора наук (DSc) в области истории и филологии для публикации своих научных результатов по своим диссертациям.

**В ЖУРНАЛЕ ПУБЛИКУЮТСЯ
СТАТЬИ ПО СЛЕДУЮЩИМ
НАПРАВЛЕНИЯМ:**

- ✓ История социально-культурных отношений тюркских народов;
- ✓ Исследования тюркского мира;
- ✓ Диалектология тюркских языков;
- ✓ Геополитика тюркского мира;
- ✓ Изучение фольклора;
- ✓ Сравнительное языкознание и литературоведение;
- ✓ Литературные отношения и переводоведение.

КОНТАКТНЫЙ АДРЕС:

Почтовый адрес:

140104, Университетский бульвар,
15, город Самарканд, Узбекистан,
Научно-исследовательский
институт Тюркологии при
Самаркандском Государственном
Университете имени Шарофа
Рашидова

Телефон:

+998 91 527 68 22

+998 99 596 35 69

+998 97 911 93 81

Telegram ID:

@turkologiya2025

Электронная почта:

turkologiya.samdu@gmail.com

Веб-сайт:

<https://turkologiya.samdu.uz>

ТРЕБОВАНИЯ К СТАТЬЯМ:

- К публикации принимаются статьи объемом 8-10 страниц;
- Структура статьи:
 1. Текст статьи должен быть выполнен шрифтом Times News Roman, размером 14 пунктов, слева: 3 см, справа: 1,5 см, сверху и внизу: 2 см; с межстрочным интервалом 1,15, формат листа А4.
 2. Название статьи, фамилия, имя и отчество автора(ов) должны быть написаны заглавными буквами в полном регистре.
 3. Должность, ученое звание, места работы(учебы), регион, Республика, номер телефона, адрес электронной почты и ORCID-номер автора(ов) должны быть указаны полностью.
 4. Аннотация должна состоять из краткого содержания и важности статьи, результатов.
 5. В начале каждой статьи, помимо языка, на котором написана статья, должна быть аннотация на 2-х других языках (на выбор – узбекский, английский, русский и турецкий).
 6. Аннотация должна содержать не более 120-150 слов.
 7. Внизу аннотации должно быть 7-10 ключевых слов, освещающих содержание статьи.
 8. Статья должна быть подготовлена в виде:
 - a) Вступление (Introduction);
 - b) Основная часть (Main part);
 - c) Результаты и обсуждение (Results and Discussions);
 - d) Выводы (Conclusions);
 - e) Литература (References) – в алфавитном порядке
 - f) Ссылка(сноски) приводится в скобках в виде фамилии автора – дата публикации – страница (Муминов, 2020: 25);
 - g) Рисунки, чертежи, таблицы, схемы нумеруются арабскими цифрами и обозначаются как «Рисунок». Знаки или указатели размещают под рисунком, в следующей строке, посередине и выделяют жирным шрифтом.
- Тема научной статьи, представленной автором (или соавторами), должна соответствовать рубрикам журнала.
- Статьи могут быть представлены на узбекском, английском, русском и всех других тюркских языках.
- Автор(ы) несут ответственность за научную обоснованность, достоверность и плагиат информации и доказательств, представленных в статье;
- Статьи рецензируются. В журнале публикуются только статьи, рекомендованные экспертами;
- Нерекомендованные статьи не публикуются и не возвращаются авторам;

“TÜRKOLOJİ ARAŞTIRMALARI” DERGİSİNİN BÜLTENİ

Özbekistan Cumhuriyeti devletinin sosyal-egitimsel ve bilimsel gelişme politikasının başarılı şekilde uygulanmasına yardımcı olmak amacıyla, Semerkant'ta düzenlenen Türk Devletleri Teşkilatının zirvesinde öngörülen karşılıklı ilişkilerin hızlandırılması için geliştirilen program ve projeleri uygulamak, bilimsel çalışmaları koordine etmek, Türkoloji alanında yürütülen araştırma çalışmaları Şeraf Reşidov adına Semerkant Devlet Üniversitesi, Uluslararası “Türkoloji Araştırmaları” dergisini tescil etmiştir. Dergi, Türk dili ve lehçeleri, Orta Asya Türk topluluklarının dil ve edebiyat ilişkileri tarihi, sosyo-kültürel alanlardaki bilimsel ve araştırma çalışmalarının sonuçlarını yayınlamayı amaçlamaktadır. Dergimizde editör kürsüsü, araştırma, bilim dünyasından, inceleme ve tanıma, bilimsel konferans, genç araştırmacı, hatıra, yıldönümleri gibi sütunlar yer almaktadır. Özbekçe, Türkçe, Rusça, İngilizce ve tüm Türk lehçelerinde yazılmış makaleler kabul edilmektedir.

Bilimsel dergi, Özbekistan Cumhuriyeti Yükseköğretim, Bilim ve İnovasyon Bakanlığı'na bağlı Yüksek Kabul Komisyonu'nun 8 Mayıs 2024 tarihli ve 354/5 sayılı kararına esasen; tarih, filoloji alanlarında Felsefe Doktoru (Doktora) ve Bilim Doktoru (DSc) akademik derecesini almaya aday kişilerin tezleri dolayısıyla bilimsel sonuçlarını yayınlaması tavsiye edilen ilmî yayınlar listesine dâhil edilmiştir.

DERGİ AŞAĞIDAKİ ALANLARDA MAKALELER YAYINLAMAKTADIR:

- ✓ Türk Dünyasındaki sosyo-kültürel ilişkilerin tarihi;
- ✓ Türk Dünyası araştırmaları;
- ✓ Türk Lehçeleri diyalektolojisi;
- ✓ Türk Dünyasının jeopolitiği;
- ✓ Folklor çalışmaları;
- ✓ Karşılaştırmalı dilbilim ve edebiyat çalışmaları;
- ✓ Edebi ilişkiler ve çeviri çalışmaları.

İLETİŞİM ADRESİ:

Posta adresi:

140104, Üniversite Bulvarı, 15,
Semerkant şehri, Özbekistan, Şeraf
Reşidov adına Semerkant Devlet
Üniversitesine bağlı Türkoloji
Araştırmaları Enstitüsü

Telefon:

+998 99 582 93 81

+998 97 911 93 81

Telegram ID:

@turkologiya2025

E-posta:

turkologiya.samdu@gmail.com

İnternet sitesi:

<https://turkologiya.samdu.uz>

MAKALE YAZIM KURALLARI:

- Makale 8-10 sayfada sunulur;
- Makale'nin yapısı:
 1. Makale metni Times New Roman yazı tipinde, 14 punto büyüklükte, sol kenarından 3 cm'lik, sağ kenarından 1,5 cm'lik, üst ve alt kenarından 2 cm'lik boşluk bırakılarak, tek sütun olarak, 1,15 satır aralığında, A4 boyutunda hazırlanmalıdır.
 2. Makalenin başlığı, yazar(lar)ın soyadı, adı ve baba adı tam olarak büyük harflerle yazılmalıdır.
 3. Yazar(lar)ın pozisyonu, akademik ünvanı, çalıştığı (öğrendiği) yer, bölgesi, cumhuriyeti, telefon numarası, e-posta adresi ve ORCID numarası eksiksiz olarak verilmeli.
 4. Özet, makalenin amacını, önemli bulgularını ve sonuçlarını içermelidir.
 5. Her makalenin başında, makalenin yazıldığı dilin yanı sıra 2 dilde de (isteğe bağlı olarak Özbekçe, İngilizce, Rusça ve Türkçe arasından seçilecek) açıklama bulunmalıdır.
 6. Özet, 120-150 sözcüğü geçmeyecek şekilde yazılmalıdır.
 7. Özeti alt kısmında makalenin içeriğini tanımlayacak en az 7, en fazla 10 anahtar kelimeye yer verilmelidir.
 8. Makale, aşağıdaki formatda hazırlanmalıdır:
 - a) Giriş (Introduction);
 - b) Ana bölüm (Main part);
 - c) Sonuçlar ve tartışma (Results and Discussions);
 - d) Sonuçlar (Conclusions);
 - e) Kaynakça (References) alfabetik olarak sıralanmalıdır;
 - f) Bağlantılar (dipnotlar) yazarın soyadı - yayın tarihi - sayfa şeklinde parantez içinde verilecektir (Muminov, 2020: 25);
 - g) Resim, çizim, tablo, diyagramlar "Resim" olarak Arap rakamları ile kaydedilir. İşaretler resmin altına, bir sonraki satıra, ortaya yerleştirilir ve koyu yazılır.
- Yazarın (veya ortak yazarların) sunduğu bilimsel makalenin konusu dergi sütunlarıyla örtüşmelidir.
- Makaleler Özbekçe, İngilizce, Rusça ve tüm Türk dillerinde gönderilebilir.
- Makalede sunulan bilgi ve kanıtların bilimsel dayanağı, güvenilirliği ve intihalinden yazar(lar) sorumludur.
- Makaleler hakemli olacaktır. Dergide sadece uzmanlar tarafından tavsiye edilen makaleler yayımlanır.
- Talep edilmeyen yazılar yayınlanmayacak ve yazarlarına iade edilmeyecektir.
- Derginin 1 sayısında yazarın sadece 1 makalesi yer alacaktır.

TURKOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR

XALQARO ILMIIY JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL OF “TURKOLOGICAL
RESEARCH”

ULUSLARARASI “TÜRKOLOJİ ARAŞTIRMALARI” BİLİMSEL
DERGİSİ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ НАУЧНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ “ТЮРКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ”

Muharrir:

Musahhih va texnik muharrir:

Norxo‘ja Choriyev

Rahmatulloh Shokirov

2025-yil 20-oktabrda tahririy-nashriyot bo‘limiga qabul qilindi.

2025-yil 24-oktabrda original-maketdan bosishga ruxsat etildi.

Qog‘oz bichimi 60x84.1/16. «Times New Roman» garniturasini.

Offset qog‘ozini. Shartli bosma tabog‘i –9.

Adadi 15 nusxa. Buyurtma №742

SamDU tahririy-nashriyot bo‘limi bosmaxonasida chop etildi.

140104, Samarqand sh., Universitet xiyoboni, 15.

ISSN 2992-9229

9 772992 922004